

DEVELOPING STUDENTS' SKILLS IN WORKING WITH TEXTS AND CREATING TEXTS IN MOTHER TONGUE EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

In the context of current demands and the growing relevance of distance (online) education, the issue of remote learning is being actively studied from a methodological perspective. At present, the effectiveness of mother tongue and reading literacy lessons is closely linked to the creation of efficient educational resources and their implementation in practice. Therefore, the development of appropriate teaching methods and methodologies aimed at achieving the objectives of the mother tongue and reading literacy curriculum has become an urgent and non-deferrable task. When creating educational resources, it is essential to take into account the specific principles of language teaching as well as aspects related to students' physiological and psychological characteristics.

In the context of current demands and the growing relevance of distance (online) education, the issue of remote learning is being actively studied from a methodological perspective. At present, the effectiveness of mother tongue and reading literacy lessons is closely linked to the creation of efficient educational resources and their implementation in practice. Therefore, the development of appropriate teaching methods and methodologies aimed at achieving the objectives of the mother tongue and reading literacy curriculum has become an urgent and non-deferrable task. When creating educational resources, it is essential to take into account the specific principles of language teaching as well as aspects related to students' physiological and psychological characteristics.

In general, secondary education, the social significance of lexical meanings and grammatical features of language units inherent to the mother tongue should be revealed, and linguistic sensitivity should be fostered in students. For this purpose, sentences or texts must be taken as a basis, since students comprehend the function of language units in expressing ideas within speech and textual contexts. The meanings of words, phrases, and combinations are interpreted based on textual content.

In primary education, partial theoretical instruction of language aims to develop students' skills in the practical and correct use of its elements. Text analysis plays a crucial

role in developing students' oral and written speech. Through text analysis, students comprehend text structure, grasp the main idea presented in the text, form attitudes toward the events described, and assimilate lexical units—words and expressions that constitute the richness of the Uzbek language. Thus, text analysis holds significant educational value.

Helping students understand the social significance of language units in human activity through texts and motivating them to learn language ensures a conscious attitude toward language learning. From the initial stage of general secondary education, the primary objective of the mother tongue and reading literacy subject is to develop the ability to appropriately use language elements in any communicative situation. Speech exists in oral and written forms. Written speech manifests itself in the form of text. A text is a unit of speech intended to be read and understood independently, without the author's direct participation. Written speech is thoughtful and refined through repeated revision.

One of the most pressing methodological issues is the development of educational requirements for students' text creation, the organization of exercises aimed at fostering a sense of responsibility, and the recommendation of methods for applying these exercises both in classroom settings and in distance education. On a broader scale, not only language learning but the acquisition of knowledge in all educational fields is carried out through texts. Therefore, the *State Educational Standard and Curriculum for General Secondary Education* explicitly states that "...young people should be able to freely, effectively, and correctly use the Uzbek language in all forms of communication and interaction across diverse social, economic, and cultural spheres, fully benefiting from its limitless possibilities and possessing the necessary skills and competencies." Accordingly, the curriculum includes topics focused on working with the lexical content of texts.

Thus, the mother tongue subject aims to form students' initial understanding of the nature of text and its significance in human life starting from primary grades. To achieve this, educational materials are selected that involve comparing sentences of different content with sentences united by a common theme and idea, and identifying the differences between them. A system of tasks is developed based on the selected materials, requiring students to engage in independent inquiry. Working with texts includes tasks such as dividing a text into parts, identifying the interconnections between these parts, determining which language units ensure coherence, selecting appropriate titles, and creating an outline corresponding to the text's content.

For example:

Task 1. Read the information given on both sides of the line. In what way do they differ? (The first column contains four sentences. The second column also contains four sentences.)

1. Alisher Navoi was very perceptive, intelligent, and well-mannered even in his childhood.
2. City residents use buses, cars, bicycles, and the metro for transportation.
3. Between the rocks, a rather large lake surrounded by wild flowers has formed.
4. The emblem of Uzbekistan depicts the Amu Darya and Syr Darya rivers.

Alisher Navoi was very perceptive, intelligent, and well-mannered even in his childhood. From the age of three, he greatly enjoyed listening to poetry and music. Because Alisher was a

bright child, his father sent him to school at the age of four. Despite being very young, Alisher studied extremely well.

(Grade 3. *Mother Tongue and Reading Literacy*, p. 18)

Task 2. What is the theme of the sentences in the first column? Based on their content, provide a title. What is the theme of the sentences in the second column? Provide an appropriate title.

Task 3. Why were you unable to give a title to the first column?

After that, information about sentences and texts is presented via the screen:

A text consists of semantically connected sentences that describe a single topic. A text conveys information about an event and can be given a title. A group of sentences that are not related to a single topic and lack semantic connection cannot be considered a text.

Students are recommended to read texts of various genres through digital devices.

Task 4. How else can the stories, poems, proverbs, and riddles you have read be called? Why? Express your opinion in written form and give a title to your response.

Task 5. How many paragraphs are there in the texts you read? Why is a text divided into paragraphs?

Students' understanding of text and coherent speech is gradually complicated step by step, and the defining features of text are incrementally expanded. In this process, it is necessary to ensure maximum parental involvement in the learning process.

For students with varying levels of achievement, different definitions of text are presented via video. Students are asked: *"Which definition of text do you prefer? Justify why the definition you chose is superior to the others."* The definitions include:

- A text is a collection of sentences on a single topic.
- A text is a written work.
- A text is written speech that expresses an event.
- A text consists of stories presented in textbooks.
- A text is a printed work.
- A text includes invitations, announcements, and greeting cards written by us.
- A text is a written narrative created by us.
- A text is a collection of sentences used to express an event in written form.

These options correspond to students' age and psychological characteristics, and students may select several definitions. The teacher then invites students to formulate their own definition of a text.

It is well known that the basic unit of speech is the sentence; therefore, a text composed of sentences is also a unit of speech. Compared to a sentence, a text expresses a more complete and comprehensive idea and conveys broader and deeper information in communicative processes. This feature is also characteristic of proverbs and sayings, which are grammatically equivalent to sentences and thus represent short texts. Consequently, it is more appropriate to study and analyze linguistic phenomena not in isolation—through individual words, phrases, or sentences—but through texts, taking communicative context into account. In this process, students must learn to identify and comprehend concepts and ideas, and to express them logically, coherently, and stylistically accurately in both oral and written forms.

It should be noted that ideas can be expressed in various types of texts, including official documents such as receipts, invitations, greeting cards, applications, announcements, and résumés. Based on systematic instruction, students are gradually taught the content, structure, and terminology of official documents through model examples.

Observations indicate that insufficient attention to text analysis and the lack of systematic text-creation exercises result in frequent errors in students' written works such as summaries and essays, as well as in official documents. These errors include inappropriate use of words and phrases, repetition of ideas, and focusing on secondary details rather than the main idea. The primary reason for this is inadequate work on analyzing texts of different genres, lack of consistency in organizing text-creation exercises, and insufficient feedback on students' mistakes.

Teaching students to fully comprehend the content and idea of a text and to reproduce it coherently requires working on the text's linguistic units, components, and title. For example, in a lesson on nouns based on the text "The Life of Alisher Navoi," the following activities are appropriate:

- Read the text. Who is it about?
- What did you learn about Alisher Navoi?
- What title has been given to the text?
- Does the title correspond to the content? Justify your opinion.
- What other titles could be given?
- Into how many parts is the text divided?
- What information is provided in the first part?
- What about the second part?
- Are these parts interconnected? Explain how.
- Retell the text. Why did you find it difficult to retell it?

Students are often unable to convey the text content as effectively as the author. To achieve this, work is carried out on the text's lexical and grammatical units.

When analyzing students' created texts, using materials from the Grade 3 *Mother Tongue and Reading Literacy* textbook (e.g., *The Timid Deer*) helps students perceive and understand how language units enhance textual expressiveness. Comparative sentences are analyzed through targeted questions to identify emotional impact, structural differences, and stylistic effectiveness.

In primary grades, texts intended for text creation should be monologic in nature, avoid unstudied grammatical constructions (such as vocatives, parenthetical words, detached parts, compound and reported speech), have a simple structure (no more than three to four paragraphs), and include tasks that require students to use the author's lexical choices, apply synonyms, and express personal attitudes toward events described. Creative tasks involving additions or modifications to texts encourage free thinking. Students are advised to draw on images, videos, observations, and personal experiences.

After preparing a draft, students are informed that editing and revising are allowed and encouraged and will not negatively affect assessment. Developing students' speech and preparing them for text creation is closely linked to systematic work with texts and the use of supplementary educational resources..

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